

Electroactive and intensified pilot-scale constructed wetlands for the treatment of high loads of septic tank effluent

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Abstract

This work evaluated four pilot-scale constructed wetlands (CWs), three of which were filled with electroconductive material to enhance the complex physical, chemical and biological reactions and one that was filled with gravel but aerated, for the treatment of domestic wastewater under different organic loading (OLR) values. The difference among the three electroconductive systems was the operating conditions (saturated, unsaturated and combination of both). According to the results, the highest COD rates were observed at the saturated and at the hybrid system. These systems were capable to remove up to 158 and 172 gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹. The highest ammonium nitrogen removal was achieved at the unsaturated system, during the second period, and was 21.6 gNH₄-N m⁻² d⁻¹.

Keywords

constructed wetlands; electroactive; intensified

INTRODUCTION

The application of Constructed Wetlands (CWs) is restrained in some cases by the land requirements, which occur to be large in case of conventional CWs, and pre-treatment is often required (UASB, French system etc.) increasing the complexity of construction and operation. One of the limiting factors in the application of CWs is the presence of adequate aeration, which aids the heterotrophs respiration that degrade the organic materials, as well as the autotrophs that convert ammonium to nitrate. The enhancement of CW performance in terms of biological and physicochemical processes can be achieved either via aeration of the bed (aerated wetlands) or with the use of alternative filling materials, that aid the metabolism of specific bacteria (electroconductive materials that involve electrochemical processes). Comparing to the conventional CW design guidelines (DWA, 2018) which is around 20 gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹, electroconductive CWs are capable of treating up to 92% of the influent organic matter under organic loading rate of 200 gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹ (Prado et al., 2019). In the same time, aerated CWs provide a higher level of treatment within a small footprint compared to conventional CWs and can provide similar to or better than a municipal activated sludge WWTP, offering an economically attractive alternative to submerged aerated filters or rotating biological contactors (Nivala et al., 2020). The main objective of the current study was to investigate the efficiency of different

electroactive CWs and an intensified (aerated) CW for the treatment of domestic wastewater (pre-treated in a septic tank) under increasing OLRs.

Influent Wastewater

Influent wastewater was pumped from the already existing WWTP of Antissa, Lesbos, Greece operated by the water utility of the island. Due to the high solids and organic load of the wastewater, especially during summer, a two-chamber septic tank was installed to reduce the load before feeding the pilot system.

Two-chamber septic tank

Septic tank was designed with two chambers for particulates' settlement and septic degradation, while the effluent was led to a third chamber (treated septic effluent), where the pilots' feeding pump was installed. Each of those chambers had a total volume of about 1 m³. The septic tank feeding rate was a critical step for the proper operation, so that no disturbance of the solids could be achieved.

Pilot Constructed Wetlands

The pilot system consisted of 4 parallel CWs (three electroactive and one intensified) operating as vertical sub-surface flow CW (VSSF CW) with a total surface of 1 m² and height of 1 m. Three of them were filled with carbon electroconductive biocompatible material, initially colonized by electroactive *Geobacter* bacteria (Figure 1) and the fourth one was filled with river gravel (inert material), while an air pump was installed to provide aeration bottom-up (6 h aeration split into 4 equal periods during the day). Regarding the electroconductive CWs, three different schemes were tested in terms of saturation; first one was fully saturated, second was fully unsaturated and the third one was practically a two-stage unsaturated on top half – saturated on bottom half. It is noted that aerated CW was, also, saturated and the aeration was intermittent so that anoxic conditions could occur. The pilot system operated for about one year (April 2021 – ongoing), while the maximum applied HLR was kept constant for a long time to assess long-time performance. Four different OLR values were applied ranging between 59 ± 8 and 200 ± 98 g COD m⁻² d⁻¹ (Table 1) and the performance of the systems was evaluated for COD and NH₄-N removal.

RESULTS

The highest COD removal rate was observed at the aerated (85-90%) during the first three periods and at the saturated system (86%) during the last period. The lower efficiency of the unsaturated wetland, regarding COD removal (45-57%) for the first three periods was possibly due to the poor solid retention, affected by the percolation velocity and the granulometry (Figure 1). However, even the unsaturated electroactive CW was capable of removing up to 86 gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹ without clogging issues, which was significantly higher than the design parameter for passive CWs (DWA, 2018), that proposes an average OLR of 20 gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹. In addition, during the last period wastewater feeding was split in a greater number of pulses (from 8 to 73 pulses), which contributed to the performance increase of the unsaturated module. The saturated and hybrid CWs were capable of removing up to 172 gCOD m⁻² d⁻¹. The unsaturated CW removed 14.5 gNH₄-N m⁻² d⁻¹ through nitrification and for the peak ammonium loading rate applied. Lower NH₄-N removal efficiency was observed for the hybrid system (25-37%), which is justified by the half volume of the aerobic zone (Figure 2). The flooded zone of the hybrid was under anoxic conditions and nitrates produced at the aerobic zone were removed via denitrification. The best ammonium removal was observed during the second period for the aerated pilot CW and was 21.6 gNH₄-N m⁻² d⁻¹.

CONCLUSIONS

Important removal of the organic loading was achieved in the saturated and hybrid electroactive pilot-scale CWs used in the current study ranging between 158 and 172 g COD m⁻² d⁻¹, respectively. The organic loading rates applied to these systems were much higher than those applied in conventional passive CWs, aiding the decrease of the required land area.

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Figure 1: MET constructed wetlands; electroconductive saturated, aerated, two-stage and unsaturated (from left to right)

Table 1: Operational periods and parameters

Period	Duration	Q (m ³ /d)	Average OLR ± Standard deviation (gCOD m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
1 st	24/06/21-27/07/21	0,2	59 ± 8
2 nd	28/07/21-02/09/21	0,3	114 ± 16
3 rd	03/09/21-24/03/22	0,4	156 ± 68
4 th	24/03/23 -25/05/22	0,4	200 ± 98

Figure 1: COD removal in relation to organic loading rate (OLR)

Figure 2: Ammonium nitrogen removal in relation to ammonium loading rate (ALR)